

CHEMISTRY OF THE RARE-EARTHS. PART I. NITRITES OF THE RARE-EARTHS

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Several series of complex (double and triple) nitrites of the rare-earths, La, Ce, Pr, Nd have been prepared and described. These have been shown to have compositions similar to those for bismuth with which the above-mentioned rare-earth elements have close analogies.

Little is known about the simple nitrites of the rare-earths. They have, however, been utilized in the separations of the yttrium earths from one another (Halden and James *J. Amer. Chem. Soc.*, 1914, 36, 1418; Hopkins and Balke, *ibid.*, 1916, 38, 2332) by fractional hydrolysis to insoluble basic nitrites. Only cerous nitrite has been described by Morgan (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1907, 91, 476) obtained by double decomposition of equivalent quantities of cerous sulphate and barium nitrite. On evaporating the solution over KOH in *vacuo*, he obtained yellow deliquescent crystals, whose analysis indicated a hydrated cerous nitrite contaminated with a certain proportion of Ce(OH)₃.

Some sparingly soluble triple nitrites of the cerium and yttrium earths with alkali metals and bivalent metals like Cu, Ni and Co have been described by Cuttica and Gallo (*Gazzetta*, 1923, 53, 374). The triple nitrites of cobalt have the general formula $5R^I NO_2, 2Co^{II}(NO_2)_2, R^{III}(NO_2)_3$, where R^I stands for K, Rb or Tl and R^{III} for Ce, La, Pr, Nd and Yt. They are not, truly speaking, complex rare-earth nitrites but cobalt-nitrites of alkali metals having the latter partly substituted by rare-earth metals; hence they may be represented as $[Co(NO_2)_6]_2 R_5^I R^{III}$. They are slowly attacked by cold dilute acids yielding $R_5^I Co(NO_2)_6$. The compound $2Co(NO_2)_2, Ce(NO_2)_3, 5KNO_2$, described as a green powder, $2Co(NO_2)_2, Ce(NO_2)_3, 5RbNO_2$, also green, and $2Co(NO_2)_2, Ce(NO_2)_3, 5TlNO_2$, deep brown all behave similarly and are slowly decomposed by water yielding cerous nitrite and cobalt-nitrite.

The analogy of bismuth salts with those of cerium earths and up to those of Gd has been beautifully demonstrated by Urbain (*Compt. rend.*, 1903, 137, 792) based on the isodimorphism of hydrated bismuth nitrates with the rare-earth nitrates and the isomorphism of the double nitrates of bismuth of the type $2M_1(NO_2)_3, 3M_2(NO_2)_3, 24H_2O$ where M₁ may be Bi or ΣLa up to Gd and M₂ may be Mg, Zn, Ni, Co or Mn. Sarkar and Goswami (*J. Indian Chem. Soc.*, 1935, 12, 608) prepared a number of triple nitrites of the general formula $C_2NaR(NO_2)_8$ (where R=Ce, La, Pr, Nd, Sm and Gd) analogous to the corresponding bismuth salts. The elements of the yttrium group beyond Gd do not form such nitrites. Like the corresponding bismuth compound, these are sparingly soluble octahedral crystals stable at the ordinary temperature in the solid state. Their aqueous solutions are slowly hydrolysed. These have been used by them as a micro-test for caesium; rubidium and potassium do not interfere.

Following this remarkable observation, the author of the present paper has considered it desirable to undertake a more detailed study of the complex triple nitrites of the rare-earths and prepared several other series of such salts containing Ce, La, Pr and Nd and Na,

K, Li and Tl with a view to accounting for such sharp difference in properties. Several series of double nitrites have also been prepared. Like the bismuthinitrites prepared by Ball and Abram (*J. Chem. Soc.*, 1913, 108, 2120) these complex nitrites of the rare-earths fall into two groups of which the general formulae are respectively $X_2R(NO_2)_4$ and $X'_2YR(NO_2)_4$, where X stands for Na, K, Tl and X' stands for K, Tl and Rb (Cs), Y for Na and Li and R for Ce, La, Pr and Nd. It has not been possible to prepare the corresponding ammonium salts owing to the unstable nature of concentrated solutions of ammonium nitrite.

Unlike bismuth, double nitrites of rare-earths with sodium nitrite $Na_2R(NO_2)_4 \cdot H_2O$ have been obtained in the solid state. The existence of the corresponding bismuth compound has been suspected by Ball and Abram (*loc. cit.*) only in solution, for deep orange coloured liquid results when bisnuth nitrate is added to a solution of sodium nitrite. This series of the nitrites of the rare-earths, however, is the least stable, quickly decomposing and giving off nitrous fumes and leaving behind rare-earth hydroxides. All attempts to prepare the corresponding lithium salt, however, have been unsuccessful as with the bismuthinitrite.

From a study of the compositions of the triple nitrites of the rare-earths, it is evident that no such compounds exist containing two metals of the same series X' or Y, all attempts to prepare them have also been unsuccessful, yielding only mixtures of the corresponding double nitrites. In this respect, these triple nitrites resemble closely the bismuthinitrites of Ball and Abran.

Of the triple nitrites the salts containing caesium prepared by Sarkar and Goswami (*loc. cit.*) are the least soluble while those containing potassium are the most soluble, the other series having intermediate solubilities.

From a consideration of the above facts, the above mentioned differences in the behaviour of caesium, rubidium and potassium salts can now be explained; for caesium-potassium salts do not exist being metals of the same series X', whereas caesium-sodium salts do so being metals of different series. Again rubidium-sodium and potassium-sodium triple nitrites, though capable of existence, being more soluble (Rb_2-Na salts moderately soluble and K_2-Na highly soluble) than the caesium-sodium triple nitrites, only this latter series of salts being very insoluble ones, are precipitated out from mixtures of the three, the other remaining in solution.

These salts are completely dissociated in solution into their constituent ions, since physico-chemical methods fail to detect the presence of any complex ion in solution. Thermo-metric and conductometric titrations of solutions of the rare-earth nitrates with alkali nitrites gave no change in temperature and no break in the conductivity curve.

EXPERIMENTAL

All nitrites used must be free from free alkali. Solutions of rare-earth nitrites and thallos and lithium nitrites used throughout the work described in this paper were prepared by the double decomposition between the corresponding sulphates and barium nitrite.

Double Nitrites of the Rare-earths.

1. *Sodium Lanthanum Nitrite.*—Lanthanum nitrite solution as prepared from 5 g. of anhydrous lanthanum sulphate and 7 g. of barium nitrite, was mixed with a solution of

4 g. of sodium nitrite, dissolved in the least quantity of water and the resulting solution was allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator over concentrated sulphuric acid in a refrigerator. After several days, beautiful crystals separated, the crystals were drained under suction, washed first with a sodium nitrite solution (25%), then with 50% aqueous acetone and finally with acetone. They were then dried between folds of the filter paper.

The salt crystallised in large, cream coloured plates, was very unstable, decomposed in a few days giving off nitrous fumes. It was highly soluble in water, the aqueous solution decomposing on heating. {Found: Na, 13'68; La, 27'41; NO₂, 54'78. Na₃La(NO₂)₆H₂O requires Na, 13'77; La, 27'54; NO₂, 55'09 per cent}.

2. *Sodium Cerium Nitrite*.—The method of preparation was the same as the preceding salt using cerous sulphate in place of lanthanum sulphate. The salt crystallised in bright yellow plates and in other respects, it resembled very closely the lanthanum salt. {Found: Na, 13'66; Ce, 27'78; NO₂, 54'62. Na₃Ce(NO₂)₆H₂O requires Na, 13'71; Ce, 27'83; NO₂, 54'87 per cent}.

3. *Sodium Praseodymium Nitrite*.—It was prepared in the same way as above using praseodymium sulphate. The salt separated in beautiful green plates. {Found: Na, 13'52; Pr, 28'02; NO₂, 54'42. Na₃Pr(NO₂)₆H₂O requires Na, 13'66; Pr, 28'12; NO₂, 54'65 per cent}.

4. *Potassium Lanthanum Nitrite*.—The salt was prepared exactly as the corresponding sodium salt (No. 1) using potassium nitrite in place of sodium nitrite. The salt crystallised in cream-coloured plates. The potassium salt was found to be stabler than the corresponding sodium salt. {Found: K, 21'24; La, 25'21; NO₂, 50'05. K₃La(NO₂)₆H₂O requires K, 21'27; La, 25'27; NO₂, 50'18 per cent}.

5. *Potassium Cerium Nitrite*.—The method of preparation was similar to above. The salt was obtained in light yellow plates, stabler than the corresponding sodium salt. It was highly soluble in water, aqueous solution gradually decomposes. {Found: K, 21'21; Ce, 25'38; NO₂, 50'05. K₃Ce(NO₂)₆H₂O requires K, 21'23; Ce, 25'41; NO₂, 50'09 per cent}.

6. *Potassium Praseodymium Nitrite*.—It was prepared exactly as the previous salt. The salt was obtained in light green plates. It was stabler than the previous one, the dry salt keeps for several days, aqueous solution only slowly decomposes. {Found: K, 21'05; Pr, 25'53; NO₂, 49'78. K₃Pr(NO₂)₆H₂O requires K, 21'15; Pr, 25'68; NO₂, 50'00 per cent}.

7. *Potassium Neodymium Nitrite*.—The method of preparation was very similar to the above. The salt crystallised in light red plates. In stability and other properties it resembled the praseodymium salt. {Found: K, 21'02; Nd, 25'55; NO₂, 49'68. K₃Nd(NO₂)₆H₂O requires K, 21'14; Nd, 25'68; NO₂, 49'91 per cent}.

8. *Thallium Lanthanum Nitrite*.—This series of salts containing thallium was stabler and less soluble than the other series containing sodium or potassium. The salt was obtained from thallium nitrite and lanthanum nitrite. Due to its lesser solubility in water it was easier to prepare being separated from a less concentrated solution than the previous ones. The salt was obtained in light orange plates, less soluble and stabler than the corresponding sodium and potassium salts. {Found: Tl, 58'45; La, 13'05; NO₂, 26'32. Tl₃La(NO₂)₆H₂O requires Tl, 58'62; La, 13'22; NO₂, 26'44 per cent}.

9. *Thallium Cerium Nitrite*.—The method of preparation was the same as in the previous one. In crystalline form and other properties, it resembled the lanthanum salt

in all respects. {Found: Tl, 58'61; Ce, 13'35; NO₂, 26'17; Tl₃Ce(NO₂)₆H₂O requires Tl, 58'51; Ce, 13'38; NO₂, 36'38 per cent}.

10. *Thallium Praseodymium Nitrite*.—The method of preparation was the same as above. It crystallised in greenish yellow plates; in other properties it resembled the previous ones. {Found: Tl, 58'32; Pr, 13'39; NO₂, 26'25. Tl₃Pr(NO₂)₆H₂O requires Tl, 58'45; Pr, 13'47; NO₂, 26'36 per cent}.

11. *Thallium Neodymium Nitrite*.—It was prepared exactly as the previous one. {Found: Tl, 58'32; Nd, 13'52; NO₂, 26'21. Tl₃Nd(NO₂)₆H₂O requires Tl, 58'40; Nd, 13'55; NO₂, 26'33 per cent}.

Triple Nitrites of the Rare-earths.

The triple nitrites are, in general, less soluble and more stable than the double nitrites of the rare-earths; the most stable and the least soluble being the series C₂NaR(NO₂)₆, previously described by Sarkar and Goswami (*loc. cit.*). Consequently, they are easier to prepare. They can be kept unaltered for months together. They crystallise in octahedral forms differing in this respect from the double nitrites.

1. *Potassium Sodium Lanthanum Nitrite*.—To a solution of lanthanum nitrite, obtained from 5 g. of anhydrous lanthanum sulphate and 7 g. of barium nitrite, were added a solution of 3'5 g. of potassium nitrite and 1'5 g. of sodium nitrite and the resulting solution allowed to crystallise in a vacuum desiccator kept in the refrigerator. After two or three days, beautiful crystals separated out. The crystals were drained under suction, washed first with aqueous acetone and finally with pure acetone. The salt crystallised in cream coloured octahedral form. It is moderately soluble in water, the aqueous solution gradually decomposing giving off nitrous fumes. {Found: K, 15'01; Na, 4'32; La, 26'38; NO₂, 53'36. K₂NaLa(NO₂)₆ requires K, 15'12; Na, 4'46; La, 26'94; NO₂, 53'49 per cent}.

2. *Potassium Sodium Cerium Nitrite*.—The salt was prepared in the same way as above taking cerous sulphate in place of lanthanum sulphate. The salt was obtained in light yellow octahedral crystals; in other respects it resembled the above salt. {Found: K, 14'97; Na, 4'41; Ce, 27'01; NO₂, 53'13. K₂NaCe(NO₂)₆ requires K, 15'08; Na, 4'45; Ce, 27'08; NO₂, 53'38 per cent}.

3. *Potassium Sodium Praseodymium Nitrite*.—The method of preparation was similar to above. The salt is obtained in pale green octahedral crystals. It is stabler than the previous salts. {Found: K, 14'88; Na, 4'25; Pr, 27'08; NO₂, 53'05. K₂NaPr(NO₂)₆ requires K, 15'03; Na, 4'43; Pr, 27'36; NO₂, 53'18 per cent}.

4. *Potassium Lithium Lanthanum Nitrite*.—The salt was prepared in the same way as salt No. 1 by taking lithium nitrite (1 mol.) in place of sodium nitrite. It separated in cream coloured octahedral crystals. The salt was less stable than the potassium-sodium salt, easily decomposed with water and could not be kept for a long time. {Found: K, 15'48; Li, 1'32; La, 27'68; NO₂, 54'95. K₂LiLa(NO₂)₆ requires K, 15'60; Li, 1'40; La, 27'70; NO₂, 55'20 per cent}.

5. *Potassium Lithium Cerium Nitrite*.—The method of preparation was the same as above. The salt separated in yellow crystals. {Found: K, 15'49; Li, 1'35; Ce, 27'83; NO₂, 54'85. K₂LiCe(NO₂)₆ requires K, 15'59; Li, 1'40; Ce, 27'95; NO₂, 55'09 per cent}.

6. *Potassium Lithium Praseodymium Nitrite*.—The salt was prepared in the same way as above. It separated in pale green octahedral forms. {Found: K, 15'42; Li, 1'30; Pr, 28'12; NO₂, 54'65. K₂LiPr(NO₂)₆ requires K, 15'51; Li, 1'39; Pr, 28'23; NO₂, 54'87 per cent}.

7. *Thallium Sodium Lanthanum Nitrite*.—This series of salts containing thallium was much stabler than the potassium-sodium or potassium-lithium compounds. The stability was perhaps due to the bigger mass of the thallium ion. For the same reason, compounds containing rubidium and caesium were stabler than the rest. The salts were also less soluble than the previous ones. The salt was prepared by evaporating, in a desiccator a solution containing two equivalents of thallium nitrite, one of sodium nitrite and one of lanthanum nitrite.

The salt separated in light yellow octahedral crystals. It was moderately soluble in water, rather stable and when dry it could be kept for a long time. {Found: Tl, 48'11; Na, 2'62; La, 16'31. NO₂, 32'45; Tl₂NaLa(NO₂)₆ requires Tl, 48'25; Na, 2'72; La, 16'43; NO₂, 32'62 per cent}.

8. *Thallium Sodium Cerium Nitrite*.—The salt was prepared in the same way as above. It separated in orange octahedron. {Found: Tl, 48'08; Na, 2'65; Ce, 16'48; NO₂, 32'48. Tl₂NaCe(NO₂)₆ requires Tl, 48'22; Na, 2'71; Ce, 16'51; NO₂, 32'55 per cent}.

9. *Thallium Sodium Praseodymium Nitrite*.—It was prepared exactly as the other salts. The triple salt was obtained in the form of light greenish yellow octahedral crystals. {Found: Tl, 47'85; Na, 2'65; Pr, 16'56; NO₂, 32'35. Tl₂NaPr(NO₂)₆ requires Tl, 48'05; Na, 2'71; Pr, 16'72; NO₂, 32'51 per cent}.

10. *Thallium Sodium Neodymium Nitrite*.—The method of preparation was the same as above. {Found: Tl, 47'78; Na, 2'68; Nd, 16'66; NO₂, 32'42. Tl₂NaNd(NO₂)₆ requires Tl, 48'05; Na, 2'71; Nd, 16'75; NO₂, 32'51 per cent}.

11. *Thallium Lithium Lanthanum Nitrite*.—The method of preparation was the same as above substituting lithium nitrite in place of sodium nitrite. {Found: Tl, 48'95; Li, 0'76; La, 16'66; NO₂, 33'06. Tl₂LiLa(NO₂)₆ requires Tl, 49'16; Li, 0'84; La, 16'75; NO₂, 33'25 per cent}.

12. *Thallium Lithium Cerium Nitrite*.—It was prepared in the same way as above. The salt separated in deep orange crystals. In other respects it resembled the other thallium salts. {Found: Tl, 48'86; Li, 0'78; Ce, 16'66; NO₂, 32'88. Tl₂LiCe(NO₂)₆ requires Tl, 49'15; Li, 0'84; Ce, 16'83; NO₂, 33'18 per cent}.

13. *Thallium Lithium Praseodymium Nitrite*.—The method of preparation was the same as above. {Found: Tl, 48'76; Li, 0'80; Pr, 16'92; NO₂, 32'88. Tl₂LiPr(NO₂)₆ requires Tl, 48'94; Li, 0'84; Pr, 17'05; NO₂, 33'13 per cent}.

14. *Thallium Lithium Neodymium Nitrite*.—The salt was prepared exactly as the praseodymium salt, which it resembled in all respects. {Found: Tl, 48'48; Li, 0'86; Nd, 16'88; NO₂, 33'25. Tl₂LiNd(NO₂)₆ requires Tl, 48'95; Li, 0'84; Nd, 17'05; NO₂, 33'13 per cent}.

15. *Rubidium Sodium Lanthanum Nitrite*.—Next to caesium-sodium compounds, these rubidium-sodium salts were the least soluble of all the triple nitrites studied. These could be prepared by methods similar to that for cesium-sodium compounds. Only more concentrated solutions were required. To 5 c.c. of 70% solution of lanthanum nitrate

were added 5 c.c. of 70% sodium nitrite solution, and the mixture was cooled in ice and filtered from any sodium nitrate deposited. To the filtrate was then added 1 c.c. of 50% solution of rubidium nitrate and kept for some time. The cream coloured crystals were then filtered under suction from mother-liquor as much as possible, washed first with 50% sodium nitrite solution, then with 50% acetone and finally with acetone. The salt separated in cream coloured octahedral crystals. {Found: Rb, 28'06; Na, 3'81; La, 22'72; NO₃, 45'11. Rb₂NaLa(NO₃)₆ requires Rb, 28'08; Na, 3'78; La, 22'82; NO₃, 45'32 per cent}.

16. *Rubidium Sodium Cerium Nitrite*.—The salt was prepared exactly as the previous one, which it resembled in all respects. {Found: Rb, 27'88; Na, 3'82; Ce, 23'01; NO₃, 45'06. Rb₂NaCe(NO₃)₆ requires Rb, 28'03; Na, 3'77; Ce, 22'85; NO₃, 45'24 per cent}.

17. *Rubidium Sodium Praseodymium Nitrite*.—The method of preparation was the same as above. The salt separated in green octahedral crystals. In all other respects it resembled the above two salts. {Found: Rb, 27'72; Na, 3'91; Pr, 22'95; NO₃, 45'02. Rb₂NaPr(NO₃)₆ requires Rb, 28'00; Na, 3'76; Pr, 23'08; NO₃, 45'17 per cent}.

Method of Analysis.

The salts were decomposed with concentrated hydrochloric acid and the rare-earths were precipitated as hydroxides by double precipitation with ammonia. The precipitated hydroxides were filtered, dissolved in dilute nitric acid and precipitated as oxalates. They were then ignited and weighed as oxides. From the filtrate ammonium salts were removed and the total alkali metals were weighed in the form of chlorides. Potassium was estimated as perchlorate and sodium or lithium, as the case may be, was determined by difference. In salts containing thallium, the total thallium and alkali metals were weighed as sulphates. Thallium was estimated as thallium iodide and the alkali metals sodium and lithium were obtained by difference. Nitrogen was estimated by conversion to ammonia by distillation with zinc and alkali and subsequent absorption in standard acids.

The author takes this opportunity to convey his best thanks to Dr. P. B. Sarkar for his kind advice and interest in the progress of the work and all laboratory facilities.

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Received October 30, 1944.